

3D Integrally-Woven CMC Compliant Structure For Turbine Engine Combustor Applications

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ABSTRACT

Integrally formed ceramic matrix composite structures are being developed for a range of hot-structure applications involving active cooling. Integral textile structures has several advantages including: 1) joints between ceramic and other materials in hot zones can be avoided; 2) thin skins (< 1 mm) can be formed that are strong and tough, enabling tolerance of higher heat fluxes; and 3) fabrication costs can be lowered by reducing part counts and steps in processing. This study addresses some of the non-traditional design and fabrication challenges that must be met to exploit integral textile ceramic structures and offers a preliminary assessment of their viability for handling the thermomechanical loads of an advanced combustor. Some design possibilities for combustors are explored for integral structures formed from ceramic fibers and matrices by weaving or other textile fabrication. The design analysis focuses on a class of integrally woven, transpiring, ceramic composite structures, which appear to minimise thermomechanical fatigue, fabrication cost, and joining problems. In particular, we will demonstrate the concept of employing compliant structures that greatly alleviate the level of thermal mismatch stresses developed during operation, while being strong enough to support the pressure difference between the internal combustor chamber and the outer coolant channels.

1. Introduction

Over the last few years, several cases have been demonstrated of the creation of integral structures formed by weaving ceramic fibers into complex three-dimensional configurations without significantly degrading the fibers' strength. The ability to weave 3D structures, rather than 2D laminates, is critical to the structural performance of brittle matrix composites. Whenever continuous surfaces of brittle matrix are present in a structure, as in any 2D laminate such as a plain weave, brittle delamination will place strong constraints on design. The only way to avoid delamination failure in ceramic composite structures is to deploy fibers in all directions in which significant loads will arise, including through the thickness of sheets and skins. Furthermore, the attachment of ceramic components to other structural materials such as superalloys is very challenging and limits design possibilities and lifetime. Forming integral structures by 3D weaving of fibers is far preferable. For example, a hot gas-facing skin can be formed integrally with walls or struts that connect it to cooler structural elements. Delamination of the skin and detachment of it from the supporting struts or walls can be eliminated as failure

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mechanisms by proper design. Finally, textile fabrication has been demonstrated for skins of thickness 1 mm or less [1]. Such fine-scale structures have not previously been available in ceramic matrix composites.

One example of an integrally woven structure relevant to turbine engine combustors is the sandwich structure shown in Fig. 1a. A hot (combustion facing) skin and a cool skin are joined by integrally woven pile yarns that can form walls dividing the space between the skins into channels. The structure is consolidated with a ceramic matrix.

The hot skin may contain an array of holes for transpiration cooling. The holes are likely to be at least 0.5 mm across to conform with current industry standards for the avoidance of blockage due to fouling. The holes can be formed during the textile fabrication process by repositioning the woven fiber tows in the hot skin. This cost-effective process can be effected without breaking or cutting fibers and therefore minimizes preferential damage initiation at the holes. In fact, holes formed in this way are likely not to be a significant cause of strength degradation or fatigue failure, because of the very high levels of notch insensitivity possessed by textile ceramic composites.

Figure 1. (a) A double-skin integrally woven sandwich, with integrally-formed transpiration holes. (b) Wood-like fracture morphology of a tough, strong all-oxide composite.

In this paper, some design possibilities for combustors are explored for integral structures formed from ceramic fibers and matrices by weaving or other textile fabrication. The design analysis focuses on a class of integrally woven, transpiring, ceramic composite structures, which appear to minimize thermomechanical fatigue, fabrication cost, and joining problems. The possibility of a very attractive design space is indicated.

Design estimates will be developed below using the properties shown in Table 1 for a representative $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{LaPO}_4$ composite of Nextel 610 fibers in a monazite matrix. Tensile strength values have been measured in macroscopic coupons. Compressive strength values have been estimated roughly in the absence of firm data. These property data must in time be developed into statistical distributions and complemented with, for

instance, fatigue and creep data, before engineering design allowables can be established. They are used here in the spirit of exploring some new concepts in an initial feasibility study. Similar conclusions concerning design feasibility are expected to apply to all-oxide composites that are toughened via porous matrices.

2. Mechanical and Thermal Stresses in an Annular Configuration

Design considerations for thermal and mechanical loads will be based on the typical axisymmetric geometry shown schematically in Fig. 2a, which is representative of an annular combustor. A free-stream mixture of combusting gases moves through the core, characterized by pressure P_∞ , temperature T_∞ , density ρ_∞ , and velocity u_∞ . Coolant is supplied via the cavity between the hot and cold skins and is characterized by pressure P_c , temperature T_c , and density ρ_c in the cavity. If transpiration holes are present, $P_\infty < P_c$. Notation for geometrical variables is shown in Fig. 2.

Stresses arise in the structure partly from the pressure differential between the combusting and cooling gases and partly from thermal strains. The stresses are influenced by the constraint imposed on various components by the geometry of the combustor. Results of simple, bounding stress and temperature analyses to be published elsewhere are as follows [7].

Table 1. Properties of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{LaPO}_4$ composite

property	symbol	estimated value
tensile strength	$\sigma_c^{tensile}$	250 - 500 MPa ^(a)
compressive strength	$\sigma_c^{compressive}$	250 MPa ^(b)
in-plane modulus	E	100 GPa ^(c)
in-plane thermal expansion	α_s	$9 \times 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$
through-thickness thermal conductivity	k_s	3.7 – 6.7 W/m-K
maximum operating temperature	T_{op}	1200 °C

^(a) Lower end of range: 0/90° plain woven laminate with approximately equal loadings of warp and weft fibers; upper end: unidirectional composites; total fiber volume fraction of 40% in both cases.

^(b) Estimated value for local compressive failure by kink band formation in a constrained small volume in the hot skin ($\sim 1 \text{ mm}^3$ or less).

^(c) Somewhat higher modulus would ensue upon achieving greater matrix densification.

Figure 2. Schematic of an annular combustor comprising hot (inner) and cool (outer) skins joined by walls or struts. (a) Unloaded and cool. (b) Deformation that minimizes thermal stress due to different expansions of hot and cool skins.

The peak temperatures on the hot and cool surfaces of the combustor facing skin, T_1 and T_2 , are

$$T_1 = \xi T_\infty + (1 - \xi) T_c + \xi Q_r / h_1 \quad \xi = \left[1 + \frac{h_2 t_h}{k_s} \right] / \left[1 + \frac{h_2}{h_1} + \frac{h_2 t_h}{k_s} \right] \quad (1a)$$

$$T_2 = \psi T_\infty + (1 - \psi) T_c + \psi Q_r / h_1 \quad \psi = 1 / \left[1 + \frac{h_2}{h_1} + \frac{h_2 t_h}{k_s} \right] \quad (1b)$$

where h_1 and h_2 are the heat transfer coefficients of the hot and cool surfaces of the hot skin, k_s is the thermal conductivity of the hot skin, and Q_r is the radiation heat flux. The cold skin will often be at approximately the same temperature as the coolant, T_c . Mechanical equilibrium between the hot and cool skins, which takes account of the thermal strains associated with the temperatures of Eq. (1) as well as mechanical loads due to the gas pressure difference, $\Delta P = P_c - P_\infty$, implies the following design equations for the extreme stresses in the hot skin:

$$\sigma_{\text{hot}}^{(1)} = -\sigma_p \left[\frac{\gamma}{3} + (1 - \eta)(1 - \gamma) \right] - \frac{\hat{\sigma}_T}{2} [\eta(1 - \gamma)(\xi + \psi) + \xi - \psi] \quad (2a)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{hot}}^{(2)} = \sigma_p \left[\frac{k_b \gamma}{3} - (1 - \eta)(k_c + k_b \gamma) \right] - \frac{\hat{\sigma}_T}{2} [\eta(k_c + k_b \gamma)(\xi + \psi) - k_b(\xi - \psi)] \quad (2b)$$

where $k_c \approx 2$ and $k_b \approx 1.7$ are stress concentration factors at the wall/hot skin junction;

$$\sigma_p = (1 - c_h) \Delta P \frac{r_h}{t_h} \quad \hat{\sigma}_T = \alpha E'_h \left(T_\infty - T_c + \frac{Q_r}{h_1} \right) \quad \gamma = \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{L}{t_h} \right)^2 \frac{t_h}{r_h} \quad (2c)$$

$$\eta = \frac{\zeta \eta_\infty}{\eta_\infty + \zeta} \quad \eta_\infty = \left[1 + \frac{t_h}{t_c} \left(1 + \frac{d}{r_h} \right) \frac{E'_h}{E'_c} \right]^{-1} \quad \zeta = \frac{r_h}{t_h} \frac{r_h}{d} \frac{c_w E'_w}{E'_h} \quad (2d)$$

and E'_h , E'_c , and E'_w are the plane strain moduli of the hot skin, cool skin, and walls (or struts) respectively; and c_w is the area fraction and L the separation of the walls (struts). The parameters ξ and ψ depend on the heat transfer coefficients and thermal conductivity; all other parameters depend only on geometry and elastic constants.

3. Importance of Compliant Structures

Evaluating Eq. (2) quickly illustrates one important goal of integral textile design. If the walls or struts can be fabricated in such a shape that they are compliant with respect to radial expansion mismatch of the two skins, then the thermal strain mismatch of the skins can be accommodated without generating large thermal stresses. Analysis shows that to achieve strain accommodation the required effective wall stiffness, E'_w , must satisfy

$$\frac{c_w E'_w}{E'_h} < \left[\frac{r_h}{t_h} \frac{r_h}{d} + \frac{r_h}{t_c} \left(\frac{r_h}{d} + 1 \right) \frac{E'_h}{E'_c} \right]^{-1} \quad (3)$$

The right-hand side depends on system requirements (e.g., size), but has values typically of order of magnitude 10^{-3} . For $c_w \sim 10^{-2}$, one must therefore have $E'_w/E'_h \sim 0.1$. Such reductions in effective stiffness are easily achieved in principle, e.g., by using the canted wall structure indicated schematically in Fig. 2b.

Given compliant walls, the peak stress (which is a design limit) on the hot surface of the hot skin varies with the hot skin thickness as shown in Fig. 3, for the heat transfer coefficients and other parameters shown in the figure. The value of h_1 has been assumed to have been reduced by transpiration to satisfy the condition that $T_1 = T_{op} = 1200^\circ\text{C}$, the maximum operating temperature of the material. This condition is discussed further below. Figure 3 shows that a feasible design window exists for skins around 1 – 10 mm thick. However, achieving $T_1 = T_{op}$, which is a separate design constraint, will impose a strong preference for the low end of this range. Without compliance in the walls, the predicted stresses are much higher in magnitude than those shown in Fig. 3, and a feasible design window may not exist. This can be attributed to the relatively high

thermal expansion of oxide composites, but it is also a factor, although a weaker one, for other ceramics.

$$t_c = 1 \text{ mm} \quad h_1 \text{ s.t. } T_1 = T_{op} \quad T_{fs} = 2230^\circ\text{C} \quad T_c = 730^\circ\text{C}$$

Figure 3. Maximum stress in the hot skin, which occurs at the location indicated in the inset, as a function of the hot skin thickness for the stated values of other parameters.

4. Benefits of Textiles at Stress Concentrations

Stress concentrations in a structure such as that of Figs. 1 and 2 arise at skin/wall junctions and transpiration holes. In alloy components, stress concentrations can be sources of serious thermomechanical fatigue problems and can limit design stresses and the operating temperature. In textile ceramic composites, the effects of the stress concentrations may be mitigated by the following phenomena, leading to wider design spaces.

Size Effects

Because of the fine scale achievable with textile components without loss of mechanical integrity and the high thermal and stress gradients present in a high heat flux application, the highest stresses in the hot skin exist over volumes ~ 0.1 mm, which are smaller in at least one dimension than a single fiber tow [7]. Small volumes of ceramic composites are known to exhibit strengths that may be 2 – 3 times those of standard coupons [8, 9]. In tensile tests, for example, strains of 2 – 2.5 % have been measured over gauge lengths ~ 0.2 mm at notch roots in specimens of woven C/SiC composites, whereas unnotched specimens of the same material fail at macroscopic strains ~ 1 % [10]. The ratio of the maximum local stress to the macroscopic failure stress is believed to be similar to that of the strains, but the laws by which the strength scales are not known. Since the gain in strength relative to coupon data can be substantial, careful analysis of this effect is warranted, with tests on prototypes to provide quantification. The benefits may be especially significant in dealing with bending stresses in the skins, which are often the largest contributions to the local stresses and are highly localized.

Figure 4. Maximum allowed value of h_1 implied by Eq. (4) for the parameter values given in the text.

Integral Forming of Holes

Stress concentration effects will also arise at transpiration holes. In this case, no meaningful estimate of the design limit seems possible without considering of the details of tow architecture. One design maxim, based on accumulated experience with polymeric textile composites, is that the holes should never be formed by machining and cutting fibers, but rather always by separating tows. Such tow separation or spreading creates a sphincter of concentrated reinforcement around each hole, which can lead to the periphery of the hole being stronger than the skin far from holes. The net effect is that instead of the hole becoming a site of strain concentration and premature failure, the skin will fail elsewhere without strength knockdown. This hole strengthening effect has been demonstrated very cogently for polymer matrix braids [11] and has now been demonstrated by analysis for oxide composite systems [12]. It has major significance in the present design problem.

5. Concluding Remarks

The optimization problem is an interesting challenge, since the problem of heat transfer with transpiration-modified boundary layers must be coupled to the problems of calculating heat conduction through the textile structure and thermal and mechanical stresses in a part in which many geometrical features can be varied in shape and dimension. Simultaneous account must be taken of thermal strains, mechanical loads, heat transfer coefficients, total required coolant flux, radiation, preform architecture, and part geometry. All of these factors are related to each other in complicated, nonlinear ways. For example, the heat transfer coefficients (and therefore the thermal fluxes) depend on the sizes of interior cavities in the proposed double skin structure and the gross dimensions of the combustor liner; the maximum allowable hot skin thickness depends on the heat fluxes and the maximum material operating temperature; the maximum allowed thermal and mechanical stresses set separate bounds on the hot skin thickness

and other dimensions; and system requirements, especially limitations on the available coolant flux, set bounds on the achievable reductions of heat transfer by transpiration.

For the material strength expected for an all-oxide composite and assuming that the heat transfer coefficients are attainable, a feasible design space (sustainable stress values) exists for hot skin thickness in the approximate range ($1 \text{ mm} < t_h < 3 \text{ mm}$). However, the required value of h_1 becomes significantly smaller and therefore any required transpiration coolant flux becomes greater as t_h increases, while more stringent restrictions are placed on the sustainable radiative heating flux. Therefore, design to reduce t_h as far as stress considerations allow will always be advantageous. Textile fabrication excels in creating structures that remain strong and tough when much less than 1 mm thick.

All predictions in this paper are based on simple stress and temperature analyses, with plausible but assumed rather than measured ranges for critical parameters, especially the heat transfer coefficients in the presence of transpiration. Obtaining heat transfer data in the relevant regime is of paramount importance. Given such data, a far more sophisticated analysis of the optimization problem will be warranted, with a systematic search for optimal conditions, rather than the demonstration of rough design windows. In the absence of such analysis, firm conclusions about the viability of ceramic composites in turbine engines are premature. In particular, current designs are not likely to express the potential of ceramics for combustor applications.

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